

Research Article

The Design, Fabrication and Evaluation of a Pedal Operated Cowpea Winnowing Machine

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Abstract

Winnowing of cowpea has been widely done manually in developing countries, such as Nigeria. The need to develop machines to ease this task cannot be overemphasized. As such, a pedal operated cowpea winnower machine was designed and fabricated in the Department of Agricultural and Bio-Environmental Engineering Department of Federal College of Agriculture, Akure with locally sourced materials. The machine which required 0.12 Kw energy was evaluated based on three different speeds of feeder rotation of 54 rpm, 108 rpm and 216 rpm and at a constant speed of fan rotation of 108 rpm. The result of the machine, after testing shows that the winnower has a maximum capacity of 374 kg/h and 90 % cleaning efficiency. This is better than manual operated winnower. Also, the optimum speed of feeder, capacity and cleaning efficiency were 195 rpm, 310 kg/h and 63 % respectively. The cost of production of machine was ₦ 66,500.

Keywords: Grains, cowpea, chaffs, optimum speed, cleaning efficiency, winnowing, Nigeria.

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Introduction

From the earliest time that man had used grain as food, the problem of removing the unwanted unedible glume, straw or husk from the actual seeds had existed (Irtwange, 1987). Until the middle of the 19th century, the principal methods of threshing grains were done manually (with hand) or spreading the ripe crops on a floor and beating with sticks, club etc. Caruthers and Rodriguez (1992) also stated that grains threshed by local method need considerable cleaning before use. This is achieved by means of wind grading for which only simple tools such as winnowing sieves were used.

Additionally, if there is plenty of wind, the threshed material is tested in the air using forks, shovels, basket etc and the lighter chaff and straw is blown to one side while the grains fall vertically. Final cleaning may be done with a winnowing basket, which is shaken until any chaff and dirt separate at the upper edge. This is very simple and effective, but at only 40 - 50kg per hour, it is slow (Caruthers 1985; Caruthers and Rodriguez, 1992).

The local way of separating seeds from the chaff was hard, dirty, inefficient, uneconomical, and slow at a time when agricultural was undergoing rapid technological advancement in most developed countries (Irtwange, 1987).

The first step in the mechanization of the threshing process came in 17th century when fanning mills were developed for winnowing. Ige (1978) built a cowpea thresher using a drum with a square cross-section in order to give a fanning effect inside the threshing unit. Teeth were welded along each edge and between two edges of the square-based prism with the concave forming a quadrant around the drum.

A major process which brings about drudgery in cowpea processing is cleaning of cowpea "winnowing". This emphasizes the need for a cowpea winnower. Such machine must be adequately designed, and should be adapted to perform under local conditions. It should be tested and evaluated before any attempt is made to introduce it on mass scale to solve the problem of availability of the machine as mentioned by Dauda (2001), it is therefore on this premise that this study was embarked upon. We designed, fabricated and evaluated a pedal operated cowpea winnowing machine.

Materials and Methods

This study was undertaken at the Department of Agricultural and Bio-environmental Engineering, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The detail of the machine is shown in Fig 1. The design of the machine and other components have been provided in details elsewhere (Olalusi and Olaborode, 2017). The pedal operated cowpea winnower was designed based on the following consideration:

1. Most of the component parts were made of mild steel and galvanized steel which are available locally, to reduce cost of production maintenance and for portability.
2. The hopper can be easily detached to allow access to the feeder and deflectors without necessarily having to dismantle the whole assembly.
3. A feeder to control the feed rate and also to agitate the mixture in the hopper was introduced.
4. The prime mover: - The machine is to be pedal operated by one person.
5. The power transmission system: It is desired that the transmission system must have high efficiency with minimum power for this reason, chain and sprocket and belt and pulley were carefully and precisely designed and selected according to the required ratio and rating.
6. Different pulley diameters 100mm and 200mm were used for the feeder of the chaff and fan shaft for speed variation.
7. The fan was designed to blow the required air velocity (V_a) necessary to separate the chaff from the grain as shown.
$$V_1 > V_a > V_c$$
8. The mixture (chaff and cowpea) was made to fall at an angle of about 45° and from reasonable height before getting to the cup stream. This was made possible with the help of two deflectors placed one after the other and at angle 45° to give the mixture initial velocity that aids the separation.
9. The two chaffs: - One for chaff outlet, while the main grain falls under gravity through the other chutes during the cleaning process.
10. The seat was made adjustable to suit different operators (Ogunmakin, 2001).

Performance Evaluation

Evaluation of the winnower was carried out to observe the workability under controlled conditions, so as to detect the specific conditions or parameters that may affect the operation of the machine. In addition to ascertain whether or not the machine performs the intended task for which it was designed. Also to know the rate and efficiency at which the task was achieved.

Test Parameters for the Cowpea Winnower

The test parameters of the machine were classified into two namely:

1. *Machine Capacity (CP)*: This is the rate at which the machine achieves its given task. It is rated in kilogram per hour for a processing machine, like the winnower

$$CP = R/t \text{ (kg/h)}$$

2. *Cleaning Efficiency (CE)*: This is the percentage mass of separated chaff after winnowing, relative to the total mass of the chaff in the mixture before winnowing

$$CE = \frac{Y_1 \times 100}{Y_1 + (Y_1 - Y_2)}$$

Performance Variable

- i. The feeder speed: The speed of the feeder affects the feed rate and the cleaning efficiency.
- ii. Nature of the mixture: The nature of physical properties of the mixture need to do with whether the cowpea mixture resulting in a reduction in the cleaning efficiency of the winnower.
- iii. Moisture content: The weight of agricultural material reduces as it is dried. This is because drying reduces the amount of moisture (water in agricultural products or materials).
- iv. The speed of rotation of the fan can also affect the velocity of the air stream.
- v. Angle of attack: The angle at which mixture is introduced into the air stream affect the cleaning efficiency.
- vi. The distribution of the mixture into the air stream, whether uniformly dispersed will not also affect the cleaning efficiency.
- vii. Based on the scope of this work, the capacity and the cleaning efficiency of the pedal operated cowpea winnower will be examined under one heading. That is, speed of feeder.

Test Procedure

The pedal operated winnower was tested using three different speeds of feed under one speed of rotation of the fan. The procedure of evaluation is highlighted below:

A. Capacity, CP (kg/h)

1. The machine was set up and ensure to be in good working condition.
2. The threshed cowpea was weighed on the balanced and recorded (R) in kg.
3. The feeder was fixed and the fan was shafted with pulleys to give the desired speed of the feeder, with respect to the speed of the fan.
4. The hopper was filled with the weighed mixture (cowpea and chaff).
5. The mixture winnowed in the machine.

6. The time (t) taken to winnow the whole mixture was recorded in seconds.
7. The capacity R/t for the treatment was calculated.
8. The procedure was repeated three times with the same speed of feed.
9. Procedure three (3) above was repeated for three treatments of speed of feeder, i.e. S₁, S₂, S₃.

B. Cleaning Efficiency (CE)

CE was performed after procedure A was completed.

1. The chaff on a nylon was collected and weighed to get Y₁ in kg
2. As much chaff as possible were collected manually from Y₂ and recorded weighed i.e. Y₂ in kg.
3. As much chaff as possible was manually picked from Y₂ and recorded as Y₃ in kg. This is the weight of the cleaner cowpea Y₃ in kg.
4. Each procedure was recorded with respect to the different speeds of feeds.
5. The total weight of the chaff was calculated with this formula: Y₁ + (Y₂ - Y₃). Where Y₂ - Y₃ is the weight of the unseparated chaff from Y₃.
6. The efficiency of the machine CE was calculated.
7. The whole procedure for the three treatments stated in section (A9) was repeated for three treatments.

Where: CE =
$$\frac{\text{Total weight of chaff blow by fan} \times 100}{\text{Total weight of chaff in the original mixture}}$$

Results and Discussion

During the evaluation period, the following observations were noticed based on the performance stated below with references to the result of the test carried out, the test parameters of the machine could be classified into two.

1. Machine capacity (C_p): This is the rate at which the machine achieves its given task. It is rated in kilogram per hour. For a processing machine like the winnower

$$C_p = R/t(\text{kg/h})$$

2. Cleaning efficiency (CE): This is the percentage mass of separated chaff after winnowing, relative to the total mass of the chaff in the mixture before winnowing.

$$CE = Y_1 \times 100 / Y_1 + (Y_1 - Y_2)$$

As stated above, the capacity of the machine was calculated using the the formula.

$C_p =$ Weight of mixture (R, Kg) per time of winnowing (h)

The capacity of the machine is about 374kg/hr which performed greater than human capacity which is about 40-45kg/hr than human capacity.

Which is about 40-45kg/hr as stated by Carruthers, (1985) and the hand operated by Mba, (2000).

Results of Performance Test

Tables 1 - 3 show the speed operations, while Table 4 depicts the results of performance tests at different speeds

Table 1: Speed of operation of machine at 54rpm

Speed 1 = 45rpm

EXP No	R (g)	Y ₁ (g)	Y ₂ (g)	Y ₃ (g)	Time (s)
1	188	11	176	175	22
2	189	8	182	181	21
3	202	8	178	177	21
Mean	193	9	178.66	177.66	21.33

Table 2: Speed of operation of machine at 108rpm

Speed 2 = 108rp

EXP No	R (g)	Y ₁ (g)	Y ₂ (g)	Y ₃ (g)	Time (s)
1	350	16	328	323	12
2	352	20	327	320	10
3	349	18	328	321	11
Mean	350.33	18	327.66	321.33	11

Table 3: Speed of operation of machine at 216rpm

Speed 3 =216rpm

EXP No	R (g)	Y ₁ (g)	Y ₂ (g)	Y ₃ (g)	Time (s)
1	416	26	378	368	4.1
2	414	27	375	358	4.2
3	418	28	377	357	3.7
Mean	416	27	376.66	359.33	4.0

Table 4: Results of performance tests at different speeds

SPEED	Time(h)	Y ₁ (g)	Y ₂ - Y ₃	Y ₁₊ (Y ₁ - Y ₃)	CE (%)	R(kg)	Cp(kg/h)
S1	5.925 X10 ⁻³	9	1	10	90.00	193	32.56
S2	3.055 X ⁻³	18	6.33	24.33	78.98	350.33	114.65
S3	1.111 X 10 ⁻³	27	17.3	44.33	60.00	416	374.40

S - speed

The capacity of the machine for various treatment using capacity
= Weight of mixture R/Time of winnowing t (kg/h)

For S1 = 350.33 X10⁻³/3.055 X 10⁻³ =114.65 (kg/h0

For S3= 193 X 10⁻³ X 5.925 X 10⁻³ = 32. 569kg/h

For S3 = 416 x 10⁻³ /1.111 x 10⁻³ = 374.40kg/h

The cleaning efficiency of the machine of various treatment, using cleaning efficiency

Weight of blown chaff/Total weight of chaff in the mixture X 100

For S1 = 9/10 X 100 = 90%

For S 2 = 18/24.3 X 100 = 73.98%

For S 3 = 27/44. 333 X 100 = 60.91%

Optimum speed of feeder = 195rpm

Optimum capacity = 310kg/h

Optimum cleaning Efficiency 62%

Conclusion

Based on the performance evaluation carried out on the winnower, it is obvious that the fabricated pedal operated cowpea winnower provided efficient way of winnowing threshed cowpea at a capacity far greater than that of hand operated cowpea winnower.

The design was a simple one which can be replicated by any engineer and technician. The parts of the machine were locally sourced, relatively cheap, and readily available. Evaluation of the winnower was carried out to observe the workability under controlled conditions, so as to detect the specific conditions or parameters that may affect the operation of the machine. The fabricated machine was tested at three different speeds. The outcome of the research was commendable. The optimum speed of feeder was 195 rpm, optimum capacity - 310 kg/h and the optimum cleaning efficiency - 63 %. It is hoped that this winnower will reduce the challenges faced by famers and processing firms.

Recommendation

1. The cowpea should be dried and threshed before winnowing to improve its efficiency.
2. The machine should operates at 195rpm of feeder speed for optimum capacity and cleaning efficiency.
3. Proper alignment should be ensured before machine operation.

It is also recommended that the winnower should be financed by the government and philanthropists, by this the price will be avoidable to end users.

PARTS LIST			
ITEM	QTY	PART NAME	MATERIAL
1	1	HOPPER	MILD STEEL SHEET
2	2	PULLEYS	
3	1	WINNOWER CHAMBER	MILD STEEL SHEET
4	1	FRAME	ANGLE IRON
5	1	V-BELT	RUBBER
6	1	FAN SHAFT	MILD STEEL ROD
7	4	FAN BLADE	MILD STEEL SHEET
8	1	CHAIN	
9	2	PEDAL	RUBBER
10	1	PEDAL STAND	ANGLE IRON
11	2	SPROCKET	
12	1	SEAT	WOOD
13	1	SEAT STAND	ANGLE IRON
14	8	SPIKE	FLAT METAL
15	1	PIPE	MILD STEEL SHEET
16	1	FAN CASING	MILD STEEL SHEET
17	4	BEARING	
18	24	BOLT & NUT	

Plate 1: Fabricated and Tested Winnowing Machine

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